

FAILURE MODE AND STRENGTH PREDICTIONS OF MECHANICALLY

FASTENED COMPOSITE JOINT

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Summary

This paper deals with the prediction of strength and failure mode of the bolted-joint in composite structure. A series of experiments which treat joint geometry, environmental temperature and clamping torque as parameters are carried out, in order to obtain the basic design data with the bolted-joint of fiber reinforced plastics. Three types of failure modes are characterized by observing damage process of bolted-joint under tension. Furthermore, the numerical procedure with the aid of finite element method (FEM) has been developed. The reciprocal of safety factor in each triangle element, which is defined in terms of the applied stress divided by tensile strength or compressive strength, is proved to be available for the prediction of the failure mode.

Introduction

It is well known that the unskillfull design of joints often causes the bearing capacity of composite structure to be reduced, even if each member in the structures possesses the sufficient strength and stiffness. Therefore, a particular attention will be required in designing the connections or joints of composite structures. Three basic types of the composite joints are most commonly used, namely, adhesive joint, mechanical joint and combination joint. The mechanically fastened joint has such advantages that the connection of the elements can be easily performed and the variation of its strength is relatively small. However there are many problems in such a joint method, which must be solved. For instance, the effects of the stress concentration around the bolted hole, and the clamping torque, and the contact problem between the bolt and the hole wall are the cases. It will be necessary to make the systematic experiment of FRP joint because of the lack of the available data for the joint design.

Several investigations concerning bolted-joint in practical composites have been reported. Some of these are the based experimental work which provided the actual strength data under the various conditions 1)-3). Other works have developed theoretical approach to determine the stress around bolt holes by means of complex functions or finite element method

4)-6). Furthermore, there are some investigations which have developed analytical procedures for predicting the strength of bolted-joint in composite materials 7),8). But, the systematic studies containing environmental condition and the effect of clamping torque are still very much limited.

In our previous works the mechanical behaviors of pin-loaded joint consisting of glass fiber mat reinforced plastics were evaluated. In the present paper the mechanical behavior of the bolted-joint are examined and discussed under various environmental temperatures and clamping torque.

Test Materials and Experimental Procedure

Material tested is the discontinuous fiber reinforced plastic laminate with quasi-isotropic property. The matrix is unsaturated polyester resin (G-753-PTW, Japan Catalytic Chemical Industry Co.) and the reinforcement is chopped strand glass mat (REM-450-G-1, Nippon Glass Fiber Co.) with 4 plies, 38% glass weight fraction. This laminate is formed to about 3mm thickness by hand lay-up method and then aftercured for 5 hours at 80°C. The configuration of specimen with single hole of 6mm diameter is shown Fig.1. The joint ratios of w/d (specimen width/hole diameter) and e/d (center of hole to edge distance/hole diameter) were varied from 5 to 9 and from 2 to 9 respectively.

Fig.1 Specimen configuration.

Fig.2 Set-up of Bolted-Joint Test.

Double-lap shear specimen with a single 6mm diameter bolt were tested in tension in order to obtain joint strength and failure modes. The tensile test was conducted by Instron type testing machine at the crosshead speed of 1mm/min. The set-up of bolted-joint test is shown in Fig.2. The specimen was placed between the two flat steel plates. Two kinds of experiments were carried out in this study. One examines the effect of environmental temperature on joint strength and damage process, and the other examines the effect of the torque clamping bolt. Hereinafter, the former is called "Environmental Temperature Test" and the latter is called "Bolt Clamping Test". The test variables selected for the present work are shown in Table 1. The elevated temperature tests of 80 and 120°C are conducted in a constant temperature chamber which was designed to

provide the uniform test conditions. The values of bolt torque clamping specimen are varied in four steps from zero to 12.8 N-m at the bolt clamping test. The test bolt was torqued exactly using the wrench with torque detector at room temperature. The damage process in various steps to failure was observed and recorded photographically. The mechanical properties of the FRP laminate tested are illustrated in Table 2.

Table 1 Test variables used in Two Experiments

	Torque(N-m)	Temperature(°c)
Environment temperature test	0	20
		80
		120
Bolt clamp test	0	20
	4.9	
	8.8	
	12.8	

Table 2 Mechanical Properties of the FRP Laminate Tested

Temperature(°c)	20	80	120
Young's modulus(MPa)	11000	8500	5700
Tensile strength(MPa)	110	98	66
Compressive strength(MPa)	237	95	9.8

Experimental Results and Considerations

The failure modes observed in this experiment are classified into three groups. These are bearing (or compression) mode, net tension mode and multiple mode as shown in Fig.3. This result is recognized to be the same as that of other works.

Fig.3 Illustration of the Three Failure Modes.

Environmental Temperature Test

It is well known that the mechanical properties of matrix and the interface between matrix and fiber depend on environmental temperature. It seems, therefore, that the bearing strength of the bolted-joint in fiber reinforced plastics may be affected by environmental temperature as well.

The photographs of the crack propagation for joint geometry of $w/d=5$ and $e/d=2$ ($5w2e$ for short) at the temperature of 20°C , 80°C and 120°C are shown in Fig.4, where clamping torque is zero. Multiple failure mode was observed at the temperatures of 20°C and 80°C as shown in Fig.4 (A) and (B), while compression mode was observed at 120°C as shown in Fig.4 (C). Whilst, it was made clear in our previous investigation that net tension mode was observed for the joint geometry of $w/d=7$ and $e/d=5$ ($7w5e$ for short) and compression mode for $w/d=9$ and $e/d=7$ ($9w7e$) at the temperature of 20°C . Therefore in this study $5w2e$, $7w5e$ and $9w7e$ type specimens are chosen for the purpose of obtaining the bolted-joints with each failure mode.

Fig.4 Crack Propagation Photographs for Joint Geometry of $w/d=5$ and $e/d=2$. Environmental Temperature (A): 20°C , (B): 80°C , (C): 120°C .

Fig.5 Load-Extension Curves at the Environmental Temperature of 20°C , 80°C and 120°C .

Fig.5 shows the load-extension curves under three environmental temperatures. It is clear from this figure that the rapid drops after the maximum load is observed in the case of the multiple and net tension modes, while the several load drops after the maximum load are occurred in the compression mode. Therefore, the bearing failure mode is considered to be most safety from the view of the failure prediction.

Fig.6 presents the relationship between joint geometry (w/d and e/d) and the maximum normalized load, where the applied load was normalized by the thickness and the failure modes are illustrated as well. It is found that the maximum normalized loads increase as specimen width, w , and center of hole to edge distance, e , increase and the environmental temperature becomes low. The failure modes at 20°C change from multiple mode to net tension mode or compression mode with increases of w/d and e/d as shown in Fig.6 (A). But, the failure at 80°C and 120°C are compression mode in most cases as shown in Figs.6 (B) and (C). These phenomena are considered to be caused by remarkable decrease of compressive strength in comparison with tensile strength at high temperature, as illustrated in Table 2. The maximum loads seems to have a tendency to have upper limit, and therefore this might suggest that the excessive joint geometry causes poor economical efficiency.

Fig.6 Relationship between Joint Geometry (w/d and e/d) and the Maximum Normalized Load with the symbols of Failure modes. Environmental Temperature (A): 20°C , (B): 80°C , (C): 120°C .

Bolt clamping test

At first, the crack propagation photographs of 9w7e specimen for the cases of bolt clamping torques of zero and 12,8N-m are shown in Fig.7, where the environmental temperature is 20°C. It is found that the failure mode of the specimen tends to change from compression mode to net tension with increase of bolt clamping torque.

(A) Bolt Clamping Torque : 0 N-m

(B) Bolt Clamping Torque : 12.8 N-m

Fig.7 Crack Propagation Photograph for Joint Geometry of $w/d=9$ and $e/d=7$. Bolt Clamping Torque (A):Zero,(B):12.8N-m

Figs.8 (A),(B) and (C) show the load-extension curves of 5w2e, 7w5e and 9w7e specimens, respectively. The bolt clamping torque is treated as parameter in each figure. These specimens seem to have a tendency to show the brittle behavior with rapid drop after the maximum load, as bolt clamping torque increase. Fig.9 (A),(B) and (C) show the relationship between joint geometry (w/d and e/d) and the maximum normalized load under clamping torques of 4.9, 8.8 and 12.8 N-m respectively. The failure modes are also illustrated in these figures in the same manner as Fig.6.

As is evident from our these experimental results, the normalized bearing strength increases with increase of bolt clamping torque and finally it approaches upper limit. The failure of the bolted-joint under the applied bolt clamping force is multiple mode at $e/d=2$ and changes into net tension mode with increasing e/d from 5 to 9 regardless of w/d . It might be thought that the net tension failure mode occurred instead of compression mode due to the constraint in the direction of the thickness to be occurred by bolt clamping force, although the FRP parts in contact with bolt are apt to occur local compression failure and its thickness become larger in the case of the clamping torque of zero.

Fig.8 Load-Extension Curves at 20°C and the Bolt Clamping Torque of 0,4.9,8.8 and 12.8N-m.
(A):w/d=5,e/d=2, (B):w/d=7,e/d=5, (C):w/d=9,e/d=7

Fig.9
Relationship between Joint
Geometry (w/d and e/d) and the
Maximum Normalized Load with
the symbols of Failure modes.
Bolt Clamping Torque
(A):4.9N-m, (B):8.8N-m,
(C):12.8N-m.

Results of Numerical Considerations

The calculation of stresses and strains in the bolted-joint was performed with the aid of a two-dimensional finite element method. Let consider the geometry discretized into 540 triangular elements as shown in Fig.10. Because of symmetry the calculation are carried out only in half of the plate. Along the symmetry axis, displacement in the x-direction is fixed. Along the lower edge of the plate, displacement in the y-direction is fixed. Point G is rigidly fixed and the plate is treated in this paper as a quasi-isotropic material with the Young's modulus as shown in Table 2.

In this study, the numerical model was proposed taking bolt itself into consideration in which the effect of bolt is expressed by the truss elements with the material constants of steel. The tensile load is applied at point O in Fig.10.

Fig.10
Finite Element Model
with triangular element
for FRP Plate and
truss element for Bolt.

The maximum stress theory was adopted here as the failure criterion of this material and thus the increase of the risk factor of the triangular element will lead to the failure of the element. Risk factors, R_T and R_C , are defined as follows;

$$R_T = \sigma_T / S_T, \quad R_C = \sigma_C / S_C$$

where σ_T and σ_C are the principal stresses in tension side and compression side, respectively. S_T and S_C are the tensile strength and the compressive strength for a given environmental temperature, respectively. The discussion will now be given on whether the failure mode of bolted-joint can be predicted by use of risk factor distribution or not.

The numerical results for 5w2e specimen at 20°C, 80°C and 120°C are shown in Fig.11 (A),(B) and (C), where the bolt clamping torque is zero and the tensile load to be applied to point O in Fig.10 is identical in the three cases. In the figure, the abscissa indicates the extension of ABCD line in Fig.10, and the ordinate is the risk factor in tension side and compression side, R_T and R_C . The increase of risk factor due to the strength reduction is observed, as the environmental temperature becomes higher. In Fig.11 (A), the risk factors become higher at the arc of BC, BC, and the edge of plate, A, than that of the other area. Consequently the damage accumulations at point A and arc BC are considered to be large, causing the multiple failure. Moreover the risk factor at point A in Fig.11 (B) becomes smaller than that of Fig.11 (A). Therefore, it should be noticed that most of the damage accumulates around the edge of hole and its failure mode changes from multiple mode to compression mode at the environmental temperature of 80°C. Furthermore, Fig.11 (C) might suggest that the increase of risk factor in compression side at arc BC enhances the tendency toward compression failure mode at the higher environmental temperatures.

Fig.11 Relation between Risk Factors in Tension and Compression Sides for Joint Geometry of $w/d=5, e/d=2$ and the Extension of ABCD line in Fig.10. Environmental Temperature (A):20°C, (B):80°C, (C):120°C

Conclusions

This paper described the failure mode of the bolted-joint of glassfiber mat reinforced plastics under various environmental conditions. The main results obtained are summarized as follows;

- 1) The failure modes of this bolted-joint are classified into bearing (or compression) mode, net tension mode and multiple mode at the room temperature. However, the failure mode come to change into bearing mode and the bearing strength decreases with increasing the environmental temperature because of remarkable reduction of compressive strength in comparison with tensile strength.

- 2) As the bolt clamping force increases, the bearing strength of the bolted-joint becomes higher and its failure is brittle, causing the tension failure mode due to the constraint in the direction of the thickness.
- 3) The concept of risk factor on the basis of maximum stress theory was proved to be useful for predicting the failure mode.

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